

Quality of Life, Work Satisfaction and Difficulties of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA

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Abstract:

Teachers' well-being and job satisfaction are key factors that shape the quality of education and drive long-term student success. This study aimed to assess the quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties faced by Filipino teachers teaching in the USA during the SY 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to examine the respondents' profiles based on age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years teaching in the USA, and net monthly income. The study also explored the extent of their quality of life across physical safety, physical health, and working environment, as well as their level of work satisfaction in terms of job security, working conditions, appreciation from superiors and peers, and recreation and social interaction. A self-made questionnaire and a descriptive study design were used to gather data from 96 Filipino teachers who were employed in the five school districts in the United States. The study found that most Filipino teachers in the USA are older, married, and highly educated, earning over \$3,200 monthly. They reported a high quality of life, job satisfaction, and significant difficulties, including cultural adjustment, language barriers, and navigating the American education system. Quality of life varied by educational attainment and teaching experience, while job satisfaction was influenced by civil status and educational background. Despite better opportunities and living conditions compared to their counterparts in the Philippines, difficulties like isolation, legal concerns, and diverse student needs persist. Recommendations include pursuing advanced degrees, cultural workshops, language training, support groups, and legal guidance to improve well-being.

Keywords: Difficulties, Filipino Teachers, quality of life, work satisfaction

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The teaching profession is widely regarded as one of the most critical and rewarding occupations, tasked with shaping the future of nations through education of their youth. However, the personal well-being and job satisfaction of teachers often go overlooked despite their direct influence on the quality of education and the long-term outcome of students (Toropova et al., 2020).

In recent years, attention has been increasingly focused on the challenges faced by teachers worldwide, especially as they navigate complex classroom environments, growing workloads, and systemic pressures. These factors have profound effects on the mental, emotional, and professional lives of educators (Nwoko et al., 2023).

In particular, Filipino teachers working abroad, especially in the United States (U.S.), have become a significant demographic in the global teaching workforce. With the growing trend of Filipino teachers seeking employment in the U.S. education system, there is a compelling need to understand the unique experience of these teachers as they adjust to a new cultural and educational environment.

The migration of Filipino teachers to the United States has been driven by a variety of factors, including better compensation and a desire to support back home (Pagatpatan-Aranda, 2023). Filipino teachers also face numerous difficulties that may affect their quality of life and work satisfaction (Ramos & Esquivel, 2018).

This study explores the quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties experienced by Filipino teachers working in the United States. Quality of life refers to a broad concept that encompasses all essential human characteristics, including both the subjective and objective assessments of the physical, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual health of an individual (Antoniadou, 2023). The difficulties, meanwhile, include the obstacles Filipino teachers face in their day-to-day roles, ranging from cultural adaptation to professional challenges such as classroom management, workload, and lack of institutional support (Yoon, 2016).

Understanding these factors is crucial, not only for the well-being of the teachers themselves but also for the quality of education they provide to students. Teachers who experience low job satisfaction or poor quality of life may struggle to remain engaged, motivated, and effective in their roles, which has negative consequences for students' learning outcomes (Ertürk, 2022). Furthermore, identifying the difficulties faced by Filipino teachers can inform policies and practices aimed at improving their work environment, enhancing retention, and supporting their mental health and overall well-being (Shaalvik, 2017).

Hence, the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to find out the quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the United States. By examining the intersection of quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence the experience of Filipino teachers abroad.

Current State of Knowledge

The quality of life among teachers is shaped by their self-attitude, work challenges, and the demands of their profession, with excessive workloads, overlapping schedules, and limited resources contributing to stress and diminished well-being (Thomas, Kumar & Singh, 2021; Goodwin & Low, 2021). Inkeles (2022) expands on this by examining the broader influences of industrialization and modernization on quality of life, using both subjective and objective indicators. In an urban context, Biagi et al. (2020) highlight the dual impact of tourism on residents' quality of life, emphasizing the need to consider community perspectives in urban planning. Additionally, De Guimarães et al. (2020) explore the role of Smart Governance in enhancing quality of life, particularly in smart cities, by linking factors such as transparency, collaboration, and accountability to sustainable development. Together, these studies provide a comprehensive view of the dynamic factors shaping quality of life across different contexts.

Quality of life is influenced by various factors, including mental health, professional challenges, and health conditions. Cleofas (2020) found that Filipino college students involved in student groups experience less depression and greater life satisfaction, highlighting the positive impact of extracurricular activities on mental well-being. Among educators, Rabacal et al. (2020) examined the effects of COVID-19, revealing moderate but varying impacts depending on degree programs, while age, sex, and proximity to cases had minimal influence. Haw et al. (2020) explored migraines among Filipino workers, identifying stress and computer use as major triggers that negatively affect both personal and professional life, though self-care and medication offer relief. Meanwhile, Aquino et al. (2020) assessed the broader impact of COVID-19, finding that emotional and mental health declined more significantly than physical health. Collectively, these studies emphasize the importance of mental health support and workplace well-being in improving overall quality of life.

Work satisfaction is significantly influenced by leadership, motivation, and workplace conditions, as seen in Haryono and Sulistyó's (2020) study on Indonesian coal miners, where leadership played a crucial role in enhancing job satisfaction. Shibiti (2020) further explores this in the education sector, emphasizing the link between work engagement and teacher retention, highlighting the need for supportive environments to reduce turnover. Topchyan and Woehler (2021) add that job satisfaction varies based on employment type and gender, with full-time teachers reporting higher satisfaction. Sahito and Vaisanen's (2020) review of studies from emerging nations identifies fair pay, supportive work environments, and strong networks as key to teacher satisfaction. Dreer (2024) underscores the psychological dimension, showing that teachers with higher well-being, particularly positive emotions, report greater job satisfaction. Collectively, these studies illustrate the intricate relationship between leadership, engagement, compensation, and psychological well-being in shaping work satisfaction across different professional settings.

Work satisfaction among Filipino teachers is shaped by various factors, including technostress, workload, work-life balance, and job security. Cahapay and Bangoc II (2021) found that while teachers remained dedicated and satisfied during the shift to remote learning, technostress negatively impacted productivity, highlighting the need for support interventions. Ancho and Bongco (2019) emphasized the excessive workload, particularly in small barangay schools, noting that while teachers strategize to cope, their well-being and personal lives are often compromised. Mercado (2019) identified a strong link between work-life balance and job satisfaction, especially among female teachers in the northern Philippines, stressing the need for solutions to improve both. Lastly, Baluyos, Rivera, and Baluyos (2019) found that while teachers rated supervision and job security highly, dissatisfaction in these areas negatively affected overall job satisfaction and performance. These studies collectively underscore the need for better workload management, mental health support, and improved supervisory structures to enhance teacher well-being and job satisfaction.

Filipino teachers in the U.S. face numerous challenges, including adapting to sociocultural and political shifts, addressing displacement-based trauma among students, and navigating curriculum changes (Lemke et al., 2021). Similar difficulties have been observed in other educational contexts, such as the UK's computing curriculum, where educators encounter both internal and external barriers but employ innovative teaching strategies like unplugged activities and collaborative learning (Sentence & Cszimadia, 2017). Language instruction poses additional hurdles, with teacher background and experience influencing how they perceive and address grammar-related challenges in

ESL/EFL classrooms (Abdu & Nagaratnam, 2011). Addressing educational inequalities requires systemic cultural and political changes, including better mentorship programs and supportive school environments (Arvanitis et al., 2021; Al Badawi, 2024). Furthermore, Gorni et al. (2024) highlight the difficulties of providing effective supervision for student teachers in geographically dispersed placements, emphasizing the role of technology in overcoming these barriers. These studies collectively underscore the need for enhanced support networks, mentorship, and technological integration to improve the teaching experience for Filipino educators in the U.S. and beyond. Filipino teachers in the U.S. face a range of challenges, including cultural adaptation, professional struggles, and microaggressions, yet they demonstrate resilience and adaptability. Modesto (2020) highlights how Filipino immigrant teachers in South Texas view their experiences as opportunities for growth, while Uytico and Abadiano (2020) emphasize the importance of mindset, independence, and clear goals in overcoming cultural barriers. Macapagong, Maguate, and Geroso (2023) identify key themes such as coping strategies and planning, illustrating the fluid nature of their adaptation process. Aranda (2023) focuses on Filipino educators in Native American reservation schools, showcasing their ability to navigate unique teaching environments. Chua (2021) sheds light on the impact of severe microaggressions on Filipino teachers in Texas, emphasizing the need for better support systems. Collectively, these studies provide a deeper understanding of the struggles and coping mechanisms of Filipino educators in the U.S., underscoring the need for policies that foster supportive and inclusive teaching environments.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on the following theories:

Quality of Life (QOL) Theory. The concept of quality of life is multifaceted and can be interpreted in different ways depending on the context. Generally, it refers to an individual's or group's well-being and satisfaction across various aspects of life, such as health, education, environment, social relationships, and economic conditions. This theory draws from multiple disciplines, including psychology, sociology, economics, and health sciences.

Erik Erikson (1982) is one of the most widely recognized proponents of the concept of quality of life, having made significant contributions to the study of human development and well-being. He emphasizes the importance of freedom and capabilities as essential elements of human development. Erikson offers a broad conceptualization of quality of life, focusing on the real opportunities individuals have to live the life they value. Central to this framework are the human capabilities necessary for a person to achieve a fulfilling and meaningful life.

In the context of teaching and education in the United States, the concept of quality of life can be used to assess how teachers' working conditions and overall well-being impact their ability to teach effectively. There is an increasing recognition that teachers' well-being is essential for ensuring high-quality education.

By applying quality of life theory to teaching, we gain insight into how teachers' personal and professional satisfaction affects their effectiveness in the classroom. Incorporating quality-of-life factors into education policy could help create a more sustainable and rewarding career path for teachers, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes and educational success.

Theories of Satisfaction. The theory of satisfaction most commonly applied in the context of work motivation is Herzberg's two-factor theory (1959). According to this theory, job satisfaction is influenced by two main factors: hygiene factors and motivational factors. Hygiene factors, such as salary, working conditions, company policies, and job security, can cause dissatisfaction if they are absent or inadequate. On the other hand, motivational factors—such as opportunities for achievement, recognition, responsibility, and personal growth—can enhance satisfaction and motivation when present. Herzberg's model suggests that improving hygiene factors can help prevent dissatisfaction, but it is the presence of motivational factors that leads to greater job satisfaction and fulfillment. Filipino teachers who have migrated to the USA are often seeking better opportunities, both economically and professionally. Applying Herzberg's two-factor theory to the experience of teaching in America can reveal several insights into their job satisfaction in terms of salary & benefits, work conditions and job security, recognition & achievement, opportunities for growth, and responsibility & autonomy. The job satisfaction of Filipino teachers in the U.S. can be better understood through Herzberg's framework by examining both hygiene and motivational factors. While they may face initial dissatisfaction due to challenges like adjusting to a new culture, work conditions, and salary expectations, elements such as career growth, recognition, and the opportunity to positively impact students' lives can significantly enhance motivation and overall satisfaction. Recognizing these dynamics is essential for policymakers and school administrators to effectively retain and support international teachers within the U.S. education system.

Theories of Difficulty. One framework closely aligned with this idea is John Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (1988). This theory explores how challenging tasks impact a student's ability to learn and how teachers can manage this difficulty. The central concept of Cognitive Load Theory is that there is a limit to the amount of information the human brain can process at once, and tasks that exceed this limit are more difficult for students to learn. Cognitive Load Theory suggests that teachers in the U.S. may face challenges in presenting information in ways that avoid overwhelming students' cognitive capacities. This can happen when instructional materials are poorly designed or when students are asked to engage in tasks that are too complex for their current level of understanding. As a result, teachers may struggle to facilitate learning effectively. For Filipino teachers teaching in the U.S., the challenges are

often compounded by factors such as a diverse student population, limited resources, pressure to perform, and classroom management issues. Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (1988) offers a valuable framework for understanding teachers' difficulties in such diverse settings. According to this theory, teachers must manage both intrinsic and extraneous cognitive load to effectively teach and support student learning. Given the increasing demands on teachers and the variety of students they encounter, strategies based on Cognitive Load Theory could provide useful insights into how teachers can refine their instructional practices and better navigate the challenges they face in the classroom.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the extent of quality of life, level of satisfaction, and difficulties encountered by Filipino teachers teaching in the USA for SY 2023-2024. Specifically, sought to answer the following questions: 1) the extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in terms of physical safety, physical health, and working environment; 2) the level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in terms of job security, working condition, appreciation of your work with superiors and peers, and recreation and social interaction; 3) the significant difference in the extent Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA when group and compared according to the aforementioned variable; 4) the significant difference in the level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 5) the difficulties encountered by Filipino teachers teaching in the USA.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research method to answer the objectives specified in this study using a self-made survey questionnaire to determine the quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the United States of America. Descriptive research is a methodology that shows design through the analysis of numeric data. It describes data that has been collected and analyzed. It can be used for significant purposes of both qualitative and quantitative research studies (Reswell, 2015). Using descriptive methods, the researcher describes the situation based on the condition of a certain phenomenon that existed at the time of the study. It is the most common means of obtaining information from the data to be gathered using questionnaires, interviews, and observations. A descriptive research design is valuable to this present study in providing facts and scientific judgment based on assessing this study. Also, this design is appropriate for the study to know the present situation and determine the prevailing issue, making an adequate and accurate interpretation of data.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 96 Filipino teachers teaching in the five school districts in the United States of America for SY 2023-2024, and since the number of respondents is quite manageable, purposive sampling was not utilized. The purposive sampling technique is a non-probability sample that is selected based on the characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Purposive sampling is different from convenience sampling and is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling (Crosman 2020).

Instruments

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire comprises of two parts. Part I. Elicited as to the name of the respondents, which is optional information as the selected demography of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, and net monthly salary. Part II. The questionnaire properly focuses on the quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA. Each area is allocated five (5) items, a total of thirty-five (35) items, and 10 items for difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA. In the area of quality of life, work satisfaction, and difficulties, the respondents were asked to rate each item according to their opinion, with 5 being the highest and 1 being the lowest, using these scales: 5-always, 4-often, 3-sometimes, 2-rarely, and 1 almost never. The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.91-excellent) and the reliability index for quality of life was 0.906, for job satisfaction was 0.982, both interpreted as "Excellent," and for difficulties was 0.786, interpreted as "acceptable," making the instrument reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher seeks permission from the school administrator. Upon approval, the researcher also seeks permission from the respondents to participate in the study before administering the instrument. After

establishing contact with the respondents, the researcher explains the study's purpose, which determined the extent of quality of life, level of work satisfaction, and difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA. The survey instrument was conducted online through Google Forms. The confidentiality and anonymity of the gathered data were emphasized. After answering the survey, the questionnaires were immediately retrieved, and the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher to solve the problem with answers and to come up with a valid conclusion.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 utilized a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of Quality of Life in terms of physical safety, physical health, and working environment.

Objective No. 2 to determine the level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in terms of job security, working conditions, appreciation of your work with superiors and peers, and recreation and social interaction, the descriptive analytical scheme and mean was used.

Objective No. 3 utilized the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test, which aims to determine whether or not significant differences exist in the areas of Quality of Life when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variable.

Objective No. 4 In terms of determining whether or not significant differences exist in the areas of work satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variable, the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test was used.

Objective No. 5 utilized the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the difficulties of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA.

Ethical Consideration

Participants' personal demographic information results were collected and were noted in the data capturing sheet. Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm experienced before, during, or after participating in the research. The data and information used in the study were treated with strict confidentiality. No statement regarding the participant's identity was disclosed unnecessarily in this study. After the data gathering, since there was no need, debriefing was not done by the researcher anymore, as cited in the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Physical Safety

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. protected by the school rules.	4.56	Very Great Extent
2. protected by the security assigned in our school.	4.53	Very Great Extent
3. provided with emergency hotlines.	4.68	Very Great Extent
4. protected by the Philippines embassy assigned in the USA.	3.89	Great Extent
5. provided by the school financial assistance.	4.19	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.37	Great Extent

Table 1 reveals the extent of quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in physical safety got the overall mean of 4.37, which is interpreted as a "great extent." Item no. 3, which states, "provided with emergency hotlines," got the highest mean of 4.68 and was interpreted as "very great extent," indicating that teachers value immediate access to help in emergencies. Item no. 4, which states, "protected by the Philippines embassy assigned in the USA," got the lowest mean of 3.89 and was interpreted as "great extent."

This implies that while teachers feel generally secure, there is a notable gap in the perceived support from their home country's diplomatic representation. The overall positive feedback indicates that teachers in the USA feel significantly protected and supported by their educational institutions and local security measures. Yet, the lower rating

concerning the embassy's role suggests that this aspect may require more attention and improvement. It's crucial for teachers to feel that they have comprehensive support, not just from their immediate environment but also from their home country.

Furthermore, while teachers feel reasonably safe due to the embassy's presence, they do not perceive it as being as effective as other safety measures. Filipino teachers may feel that the support or protection provided by the Philippines embassy is limited in scope or not as readily accessible compared to other forms of support, such as emergency hotlines or school security.

As mentioned in the study of Tabuga et al. (2021), OFWs are protected while working overseas, and the temporary income generated from it aids in building up their resilience when they return to the country for good. It is also important to note that such vulnerable workers are also in the bottom income classes. Government agencies mandated to promote the welfare of migrant workers in terms of their physical safety.

Table 2

Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Physical Health

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. provided by our school health insurance.	4.63	Very Great Extent
2. free with social services.	4.24	Great Extent
3. having our yearly physical checkup.	4.72	Very Great Extent
4. provided with a balanced diet food in our school.	3.96	Great Extent
5. having enough time to exercise every day.	3.18	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	4.14	Great Extent

Table 2 shows the extent of the quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in terms of physical health. They got an overall mean of 4.14 and are interpreted as "great extent." Item No. 3, which states, "having our yearly physical checkup," got the highest mean of 4.72 and interpreted as "very great extent," while Item No. 5, which states, "having enough time to exercise every day," got the lowest mean of 3.18, and interpreted as "moderate extent."

While teachers feel well-supported in terms of health insurance and regular checkups, the lower score for exercise time suggests a gap in promoting physical well-being within their daily schedules. This indicates a need for schools to prioritize not just providing health services but also fostering an environment that encourages physical activity.

Teachers may have demanding schedules that leave little time for daily exercise. Long working hours, preparation time, and other responsibilities could reduce the time available for physical activity. Also, high levels of stress and fatigue from teaching responsibilities can affect motivation and energy levels for exercising. As cited in the study of Carroll, A. (2022), workload is one of the most frequently cited sources of teacher stress, particularly as the profession experiences a process of intensification. Thus, teachers prioritize rest and relaxation over physical exercise due to exhaustion.

Table 3

Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Working Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. provided with conducive classrooms in the school.	4.34	Great Extent
2. provided with my comfortable shelter.	4.38	Great Extent
3. provided with high-technology gadgets in school.	4.49	Great Extent
4. provided with high-definition visual aids.	4.44	Great Extent
5. having a harmonious relationship with my colleagues	4.46	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.42	Great Extent

Table 3 reveals the extent of quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in a working environment, revealing an overall mean of 4.42 and interpreted as "great extent." Item No. 3, which states, "provided with high-technology gadgets in school," got the highest mean of 4.49, reflecting a strong sense of support and resources in the teaching environment, particularly in terms of technology and collegial relationships, while Item No. 1, which states, "provided with conducive classrooms in the school" got the lowest mean of 4.34.

This result implies that while teachers generally find their working environment satisfactory, there may be specific issues related to classroom conditions that are less favorable compared to other aspects. Teachers might have higher expectations for what constitutes a "conducive" classroom environment. If their classrooms do not fully meet these expectations in terms of comfort, size, or functionality, this could contribute to a lower rating. Teachers believe that providing students with a conducive classroom can contribute to better learning for each student.

Assahrawiza et. al. (2024) emphasized that to build an efficient learning environment, it is important to foster a sense of comfort, enjoyment, and motivation, which serves as a catalyst and incentive for student learning.

Table 4
Level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Job Security

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. satisfied with the sustainability and stability of my work.	4.32	High Level
2. satisfied with the workload and having less paperwork.	4.26	High Level
3. satisfied with my life and able to help my family.	4.30	High Level
4. satisfied with the professional growth offered by the school.	4.35	High Level
5. satisfied with my salary and benefits.	4.39	High Level
Overall Mean	4.33	High Level

Table 4 shows the results on the level of work satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in terms of job security. The result shows an overall mean of 4.33, which is interpreted as "high level," and Item No. 5, which states "satisfied with my salary and benefits," got the highest mean of 4.39, while Item No. 2, which states "satisfied with the workload and having less paperwork" got the lowest mean of 4.26 and both interpreted as "high level."

Their positive feelings about workload, salary, benefits, and professional growth contribute significantly to their overall happiness. However, the slight dip in satisfaction regarding workload and paperwork indicates a potential area for improvement. It reflects a common concern among educators who may feel uncertain about their future in the profession.

Although both are interpreted as high levels, teachers are less satisfied with the workload and have less paperwork due to Teachers often facing a significant workload that extends beyond classroom teaching. This includes lesson planning, grading, attending meetings, and managing extracurricular activities. Even if the paperwork itself is not excessive, the overall workload can be overwhelming. To combat this, creating a positive and supportive workplace is critical in enhancing employee well-being, job satisfaction, and performance (Liang et al., 2024).

Table 5
Level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Working Condition

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. satisfied with my work descriptions.	4.31	High Level
2. satisfied with my assigned workload.	4.30	High Level
3. satisfied with my work sustainability and stability.	4.32	High Level
4. satisfied with my salary and benefits offered.	4.40	High Level
5. satisfied with the support given by my school.	4.40	High Level
Overall Mean	4.35	High Level

Table 5 shows the results on the level of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in working conditions, which got an overall mean of 4.35 and was interpreted as "high level." Item No.4, which states, "satisfied with my salary and benefits offered," and Item No. 5, which states, "satisfied with the support given by my school," got the highest mean of 4.40, and item no. 2, which states, "satisfied with my assigned workload" got the lowest mean of 4.30, both interpreted as "high level."

The results suggest that while teachers are generally content with their workload, certain concerns remain. Teachers may face significant demands and responsibilities that, though manageable, might not align perfectly with ideal conditions. Even when workloads are perceived as reasonable, they can still contribute to stress, particularly when discrepancies exist between anticipated and actual responsibilities. Some teachers feel their workloads are heavier or more complex than expected. Addressing these issues and refining workload management strategies to better meet teachers' expectations could enhance overall job satisfaction and improve their working environment.

Aligned with the study of Dreer (2021) the job-related well-being of teachers, especially positive emotions in the workplace, play an important role in teachers' job satisfaction and their subsequent retention. With teacher shortages around the world and high attrition rates in some countries, teachers who experience high job satisfaction offer solid support for school systems as they are healthier, more productive, and more likely to retain their jobs in the long term.

Table 6

Level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Appreciation of Your Work with Superiors and Peers

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. showed a harmonious relationship with my colleagues.	4.54	Very High Level
2. appreciated in the teaching-learning process and creativity.	4.39	High Level
3. given good and positive feedback during my classroom observations.	4.47	High Level
4. given recognition of my teaching performance.	4.36	High Level
5. given the appreciation for sharing my strategies, methods, and approach to teaching.	4.38	High Level
Overall Mean	4.43	High Level

Table 6 reveals the result on the level of work satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in appreciation of their work with superiors and peers, which got an overall mean of 4.43 and was interpreted as "high level." Item No.1, which states, "showed a harmonious relationship with my colleagues," got the highest mean of 4.54, interpreted as "very high level." Item No. 4, which states, "given recognition of my teaching performance," got the lowest mean of 4.36, and interpreted as "high level." Although it still falls within the high satisfaction range, it is the lowest among the items assessed. While Filipino teachers generally feel supported and appreciated in their roles, the slightly lower score in recognition of their teaching performance indicates a potential gap. This suggests that while teachers experience a collaborative environment and receive feedback, they may still feel that their individual contributions and achievements are not sufficiently acknowledged.

Teachers might feel that the recognition for their teaching performance is not as consistent or widespread as other forms of appreciation. Recognition might be more sporadic or less formalized compared to other types of feedback. Being given recognition has a big impact on boosting the morale of the teachers. Haryono and Sulisty (2020) research emphasized the ripple effect and how job happiness is a key factor in overall employee performance and a fundamental motivator of success in the workplace.

Table 7

Level of work satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Recreation and Social Interaction

Items	Mean	Interpretation
Teacher in USA is...		
1. given the opportunity to travel in different states and nearby countries.	3.65	High Level
2. given the chance to participate in team building.	4.42	High Level
3. given the opportunity to attend seminars and workshops.	4.48	High Level
4. given the opportunity to participate in capacity building.	4.38	High Level
5. given the chance to share my expertise in my subject area and experiences aligned to my teaching job.	4.41	High Level
Overall Mean	4.26	High Level

Table 7 reveals the result on the level of work satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in recreation and social interaction, which got an overall mean of 4.26 and was interpreted as "high level." Item No.3, which states, "given the opportunity to attend seminars and workshops," got the highest mean of 4.48, while Item No. 1, which states, "given the opportunity to travel in different states and nearby countries," got the lowest mean of 3.65, interpreted as "high level."

While Filipino teachers report a positive experience in professional development and social interaction, the lower satisfaction score regarding travel opportunities suggests that many teachers may feel limited in their recreational options. This may impact their overall well-being and work-life balance, as travel and exploration can be vital for relaxation and personal growth.

Teachers value the professional development opportunities provided to them. Attending seminars and workshops and benchmarking to other school districts likely contributes to their work satisfaction by offering avenues for skill enhancement, networking, and staying updated with educational trends. According to Pantaleon, M. J. (2024), career growth or planning through attending seminars and workshops is a deliberate and ongoing process that individuals engage in to advance their careers and achieve personal and professional fulfillment. It involves setting goals, acquiring new skills, seeking out development opportunities, and making strategic decisions that align with one's aspirations.

Table 8

Differences in the Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Physical Safety when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	47.15	1084.500	0.656		Not Significant
	Older	52	49.64				
Civil Status	Single	30	43.30	834.000	0.209		Not Significant
	Married	66	50.86				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	34.45	558.500	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Higher	68	54.29				
Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	40.65	806.000	0.017		Significant
	Longer	56	54.11				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	47.62	1110.000	0.757		Not Significant
	Higher	49	49.35				

Table 8 reveals the difference in the extent of quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in physical safety when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, civil status, and net monthly income with *p*-values of 0.656, 0.209, and 0.757, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the quality of life of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, civil status, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

On the other hand, a significant difference exists between the variables of highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching in the USA, with *p*-values of 0.001 and 0.017, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the quality of life of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching in the USA is hereby rejected.

The findings suggest that educational background and number of years of teaching experience significantly influence Filipino teachers' perceived quality of life in terms of physical safety. Higher educational attainment and more extended experience correlate with a greater sense of security, which could be tied to better preparedness for challenges faced in the classroom and a deeper understanding of their work environment. While age, civil status, and net monthly income can influence aspects of quality of life, other factors like job satisfaction, benefits, and support systems play a more significant role in creating a relatively uniform quality of life among Filipino teachers in the USA.

Thus, teachers need support from their superiors, family, and friends. As per the study it is imperative that we give all the necessary support for all the teachers. One way of giving support is through empowerment. To empower our teachers, we need to look first for their welfare, beliefs, longings, perspective, and, more importantly, their aspirations and dreams for their professional and personal lives. Teachers, being an important human resource in schools, must be given enough importance and support (Aquino et al., 2023).

Table 9

Difference in the Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Physical Health when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	48.48	1143.000	0.994		Not Significant
	Older	52	48.52				
Civil Status	Single	30	45.47	899.000	0.467		Not Significant
	Married	66	49.88				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	40.95	740.500	0.085	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	68	51.61				
Number of Years Teaching in USA	Shorter	40	45.14	985.500	0.312		Not Significant
	Longer	56	50.90				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	50.96	1036.000	0.392		Not Significant
	Higher	49	46.14				

Table 9 reveals the difference in the extent of quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in physical health when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in all variables; therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the quality of life of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" is hereby accepted.

The lack of significant differences across various demographic variables suggests that physical health quality of life for Filipino teachers in the USA is largely uniform, regardless of age, marital status, educational attainment, teaching experience, or income level. This uniformity might indicate that the challenges and supports affecting teachers' physical health are broadly experienced across the board, making targeted interventions less critical based on these factors alone.

According to Tarraya (2023), teachers' challenges impact their overall work performance, mental and physical health, and even personal lives. Hence, while changes and improvement in public policies necessitate thorough studies, it is strongly encouraged that teachers should practice work-life balance, establish time and emotional management, set boundaries between personal and professional interactions, and continue pursuing ways to improve themselves. A physically and mentally healthy teacher works effectively and efficiently and will significantly impact the lives of the learners and community.

Table 10
Difference in the Extent of Quality of Life of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in a Working Environment when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	45.26	1001.500	0.284		Not Significant
	Older	52	51.24				
Civil Status	Single	30	42.72	816.500	0.161		Not Significant
	Married	66	51.13				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	34.66	564.500	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Higher	68	54.20				
Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	45.93	1017.000	0.434		Not Significant
	Longer	56	50.34				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	43.85	933.000	0.102		Not Significant
	Higher	49	52.96				

Table 10 reveals the difference in the extent of quality of life of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in a working environment when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income with *p*-values of 0.284, 0.161, 0.434, and 0.102, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the quality of life of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

However, a significant difference exists in the variable of highest educational attainment with a *p*-value of 0.001. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the quality of life of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of highest educational attainment is hereby rejected.

The significant disparity in working environment quality based on educational attainment suggests that higher qualifications may correlate with better job satisfaction and working conditions. This could stem from a variety of factors, including more opportunities for professional development, better job security, and greater recognition within the educational system. Conversely, the absence of significant differences across other demographic variables implies that the working environment's challenges are shared among teachers, regardless of their personal circumstances.

The results of the study showed that, in spite of the difficulties posed by the shift to remote education, high school instructors generally had a good attitude toward their employment. Appropriate workloads and cozy working environments both contributed to this contentment. Even in the midst of challenging circumstances, aspects like workload management and fostering a healthy work environment are critical in determining teacher satisfaction (Malquisto et al., 2023).

Table 11

Difference in the Level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Job Security when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	42.85	895.500	0.062		Not Significant
	Older	52	53.28				
Civil Status	Single	30	39.03	706.000	0.022		Significant
	Married	66	52.80				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	32.38	500.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	68	55.14				
Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	43.84	933.500	0.157		Not Significant
	Longer	56	51.83				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	43.68	925.000	0.090		Not Significant
	Higher	49	53.12				

Table 11 reveals the difference in job security levels of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income with *p*-values of 0.062, 0.157, and 0.090, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

However, a significant difference exists in the variable of civil status and highest educational attainment with *p*-values of 0.022 and 0.000. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of civil status and highest educational attainment is hereby rejected.

The data indicates that marital status and educational attainment significantly influence job satisfaction among Filipino teachers in terms of job security. Married teachers may experience enhanced job security due to shared financial responsibilities or support systems, while higher educational attainment likely leads to better job opportunities, stability, and recognition within their roles. The lack of significant findings related to age, teaching experience, and income suggests that these factors may not play a crucial role in determining job security perceptions among teachers.

The study conducted by Baluyos et al. (2019) examines the correlation between teachers' job satisfaction and work performance in the Philippines. The study finds a negative association between teachers' job security and contentment with supervision, even though both factors were given high ratings.

Table 12
Difference in the Level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Working Conditions when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	43.41	920.000	0.088		Not Significant
	Older	52	52.81				
Civil Status	Single	30	39.10	708.000	0.021	0.05	Significant
	Married	66	52.77				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	35.39	585.000	0.002		Significant
	Higher	68	53.90				

Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	45.01	980.500	0.283	Not Significant
	Longer	56	50.99			
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	44.61	968.500	0.164	Not Significant
	Higher	49	52.23			

Table 12 reveals the difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in terms of working conditions when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income with p -values of 0.088, 0.283, and 0.164, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

However, a significant difference exists in the variable of civil status and highest educational attainment with p -values of 0.021 and 0.002. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of civil status and highest educational attainment is hereby rejected.

The findings suggest that both marital status and educational attainment significantly influence the job satisfaction of Filipino teachers regarding their working conditions. Married teachers may benefit from shared responsibilities and support systems that enhance their job satisfaction. Additionally, higher educational attainment leads to better job conditions, recognition, and opportunities for professional growth. When grouped by age, years of teaching in the USA, and net monthly income, there is no discernible variation in job satisfaction based on working conditions. This can be attributed to consistent working conditions, teachers' effective adaptation, the stabilizing effect of income and institutional support, and the relative impact of other factors influencing job satisfaction.

The research study conducted by Baluyos et al. (2019) highlights the need for enhanced support systems in these particular areas to raise teachers' overall job satisfaction and effectiveness.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Appreciation of Your Work with Superiors and Peers when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	44.63	973.500	0.190		Not Significant
	Older	52	51.78				
Civil Status	Single	30	40.72	756.500	0.054		Not Significant
	Married	66	52.04				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	39.64	704.000	0.037	0.05	Significant
	Higher	68	52.15				
Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	44.28	951.000	0.189		Not Significant
	Longer	56	51.52				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	46.06	1037.000	0.381		Not Significant
	Higher	49	50.84				

Table 13 reveals the difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in Appreciation of their work with superiors and peers when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income with p -values of 0.190, 0.054, 0.189, and 0.381, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

However, a significant difference exists in the variable of highest educational attainment with p -value of 0.037. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of highest educational attainment is hereby rejected.

The findings indicate that educational attainment is a critical factor influencing how Filipino teachers perceive appreciation in their work environment. Those with higher education levels not only feel more valued but are likely

to receive better recognition from peers and superiors. When grouped by age, civil status, number of years spent teaching, and net monthly income, there was no discernible variation in job satisfaction based on work appreciation from peers and superiors. This lack of variation can be attributed to many factors, including cultural norms, standardized appreciation practices, the relative importance of other job satisfaction drivers, and teachers' adaptation to these differences.

Thus, we can build a more supportive and inclusive educational system that benefits both teachers and students by appreciating the value of teachers and giving them the assistance and resources they require (Roque et al., 2024).

Table 14

Difference in the Level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers teaching in the USA in Recreation and Social Interaction when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	44	45.85	1027.500	0.386		Not Significant
	Older	52	50.74				
Civil Status	Single	30	43.47	839.000	0.227		Not Significant
	Married	66	50.79				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	36.80	624.500	0.008	0.05	Significant
	Higher	68	53.32				
Number of Years Teaching in the USA	Shorter	40	44.45	958.000	0.223		Not Significant
	Longer	56	51.39				
Net Monthly Income	Lower	47	46.29	1047.500	0.440		Not Significant
	Higher	49	50.62				

Table 14 reveals the difference in the Level of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers teaching in the USA in recreation and social interaction when grouped and compared according to variables. The table showed no significant difference in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income with *p*-values of 0.386, 0.227, 0.223, and 0.440, respectively. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of age, civil status, number of years in teaching in the USA, and net monthly income is hereby accepted.

However, a significant difference exists in the variable of highest educational attainment with *p*-value of 0.008. Therefore, the hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of Filipino Teachers Teaching in the USA when grouped and compared according to the variables" in the variable of highest educational attainment is hereby rejected.

The results highlight that educational attainment plays a crucial role in shaping Filipino teachers' recreational and social experiences. Those with higher education levels report greater satisfaction with their social interactions, which contributes to overall job satisfaction and a sense of belonging in their workplace. Conversely, teachers with lower educational backgrounds may feel less connected and engaged, impacting their overall well-being.

Due in large part to higher expectations for work-life balance, the necessity of effective coping mechanisms, the significance of professional networking and collegial relationships, and alignment with institutional culture, recreation and social interaction have a significant impact on job satisfaction among Filipino teachers in the USA, especially when analyzed by highest educational attainment. These elements are vital for sustaining job satisfaction for advanced degree holders who teach since they enhance their general well-being and sense of fulfillment in their careers. Various factors, including uniformity in opportunities, the dominance of other satisfaction drivers, adaptation to the work environment, differing personal priorities, and institutional culture, can be blamed for the lack of significant impact that social interaction and recreation have on job satisfaction among Filipino teachers, regardless of their age, civil status, net monthly income, or length of service. Together, these elements lessen the proportional impact of social and recreational activities on job satisfaction in a variety of professional and demographic contexts (Ladica et al., 2024).

Conclusions

Filipino teachers in the U.S. generally enjoy a higher quality of life than their counterparts in the Philippines due to better job opportunities, salaries, and living conditions, alongside strong job satisfaction from supportive work environments, professional growth, and community engagement. However, they also face significant challenges,

including cultural adjustment, language barriers, differences in educational systems, and legal uncertainties, leading to stress and isolation. Quality of life varies based on factors like physical safety and work environment, while job satisfaction is influenced by job security, working conditions, and professional recognition. To navigate these challenges, aspiring Filipino teachers are advised to complete advanced degrees, attend cultural and educational workshops, participate in mentorship programs, and train in culturally responsive teaching. Enrolling in language classes, joining support groups, staying connected with family, and seeking legal guidance can further ease their transition and enhance their overall experience in the U.S.

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